

FRACTURE CHARACTERISTICS OF DIFFERENT FIBERS IN FIBER
REINFORCED ALUMINUMS AS DETECTED BY ACOUSTIC EMISSION

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Experimental acoustic emission techniques of sound detection and analyses of pulse rate and pulse count as a means of evaluating fiber reinforced composites are discussed. Since the stress-strain relationship for the composite, before fracture, was also obtained using conventional mechanical tension test equipment, it was possible to detect that region (strain) where significant fiber fracture began for a particular composite specimen. The composite materials of interest included graphite fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 7000, boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 6061, and boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 2024.

Introduction

The high specific strength and modulus of aluminum reinforced with high performance fibers such as graphite and boron make these composites extremely promising for use as structural elements in critical areas of Army aircraft. One important method for improving such composites involves the study and understanding of their deformation and fracture modes, and fiber distribution within the matrix material.

In this report, experimental acoustic emission techniques of sound detection and analyses of pulse rate and pulse count as a means of evaluating fiber reinforced composites during deformation are discussed. Since the stress-strain relationship for the composite, before fracture, was also obtained using conventional mechanical tension test equipment, it was possible to detect that region of strain where significant fiber fracture began for a particular composite specimen. The composite materials studied included graphite fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 7000, boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 6061, and boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 2024. Some experimental and analytical studies have been previously made with boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 2024, and the technical results, contained in references 1 and 2, have also been used in this study.

Materials

Although specific specimen fabrication processes will not be described here, the aluminum fiber reinforced specimens, used in this study, were fabricated using liquid metal infiltration techniques or diffusion bonding techniques combined with hot pressing. Specimens of aluminum alloy 7000 containing uniaxial graphite fibers were made having dimensions on the order of 5.0" x 0.25" x 0.04". Aluminum alloy 6061 and aluminum alloy 2024 specimens containing uniaxial boron fibers, but with different fiber diameters, were machined from larger plates of two different thicknesses; specimen dimensions were on the order of 5.0" x 0.20" x 0.04" and 6.5" x 0.19" x 0.10", respectively. All specimens were flat and rectangular; and subsequent longitudinal tensile stresses were applied parallel to the fibers which were uniaxially aligned along the length of the specimen. An unreinforced specimen of aluminum alloy 2024, having the approximate dimensions 6.5" x 0.20" x 0.08", was also tested in order to compare its acoustic emission characteristics with its fiber reinforced counterparts.

In any comparison of materials data, consideration has to be given to the fact that specimen sizes may differ and any interpretations of the data has to take this into account. However, in reference to acoustic emission data, as well as mechanical properties data, it is the form of the data obtained on recorders, for

example, that supplies much useful information. There were four categories of specimens used. Typical composite constituents are listed below.

- I. Matrix: Aluminum 7000 (5% Zn, 0.5% Mg)
Fibers: Thornel 50 (graphite)
Fiber Diameter: 6.6 microns (average)
Volume Fraction: 31-36%
Number of Fibers: 60,000 - 70,000

- II. Matrix: Aluminum 6061 (1.0% Mg, 0.6% Si, 0.25% Cu, 0.25% Cr)
Fibers: Boron
Fiber Diameter: 5.6 mils (tungsten inner core)
Volume Fraction: 45% - 50%
Number of Fibers: 150 - 170

- III. Matrix: Aluminum 2024 (4.5% Cu, 1.5% Mg, 0.6% Mn)
Fibers: Boron
Fiber Diameter: 4.0 mils (tungsten inner core)
Volume Fraction: 40%
Number of Fibers: 600

- IV. Aluminum 2024 (4.5% Cu, 1.5% Mg, 0.6% Mn)

This report presents, for each material tested, data on fracture stress and strain, acoustic emission count, and acoustic emission rate.

Test Equipment

The acoustic emission equipment was composed of an acoustic emission unit and a mechanical tension test unit. The acoustic emission unit consisted of a preamplifier and amplifier having a gain selectable up to 100 db and having a bandwidth ranging from 100k Hz to 2000k Hz; a totalizer having selectable pass bands, digital-to-analog conversion output, and a digital readout display; an audio monitor having a speaker and amplifier with volume control; power supply and module housings; and a transducer for detecting acoustic emission at a peak response of 115k Hz $\pm 5\%$. The acoustic emission equipment had the capability of recording the total acoustic emission count (events) and acoustic emission rate on x-y-y' recorders together with the stress-strain relationship of the pertinent specimen when subjected to stress. An emission event is defined as a rapid physical change in a material, such as the breaking of a fiber in a composite, that releases energy which appears as acoustic emission. (3)

The mechanical tension test unit (Instron Model TT-C) was adjusted to have a head speed of 0.020 in/min for all tests; and

an extensometer was used to detect the stress-strain response from the specimen. A gage length of 1.00 inch was used with the aluminum 6061 composite specimens, while a gage length of 2.00 inches was used with the remaining specimens. Figure 1 shows the overall acoustic emission equipment.

Results and Discussion

The emphasis in this study was on fiber fracture characteristics as detected by acoustic emission techniques. It was believed that the acoustic emission emanating from the fiber reinforced composite under stress would be due to many factors but primarily to multiple fiber fracture and fiber pullout associated with interface failure and matrix failure. Of interest also were the kinds of acoustic emission and the variations in acoustic emission which could be obtained for the different composite materials.

Figure 2 is a representative photomicrograph of graphite fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 7000 taken from a section of an unstressed specimen. It shows the structure and alignment of the graphite fibers in the matrix. Although the fibers from this section are well distributed, some fibers can be seen touching each other. It should also be noted that fiber cross-sectional areas are not circular so that when reference is made to fiber diameters of 6.6 microns, this value must be considered to be an average value.

Figure 3a shows the acoustic emission count and composite stress as a function of composite strain for graphite fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 7000 (the specimen cross-sectional area is 0.249" x 0.041"; the number of fibers ranges from 59,700 to 69,300); and Figure 3b shows the acoustic emission rate and stress as a function of strain for the same specimen. It can be noted that the acoustic emission count is relatively small until a composite strain near 0.0025 in/in is reached. Beyond this strain value of 0.0025 in/in, the acoustic emission count begins to increase very rapidly until composite fracture is reached (14,896 counts, near fracture); during this same time, the acoustic emission rate also increases rapidly (probably reaching 200 counts/sec, near fracture). Figure 4, again, shows the acoustic emission count and composite stress as a function of composite strain for another similar specimen (the specimen cross-sectional area is 0.252" x 0.039"; the number of fibers ranges from 57,500 to 66,700). The acoustic emission data here is similar to that contained in Figure 3a except that the acoustic emission count is smaller (9,648 counts, near fracture).

In reviewing the acoustic emission data from Figure 3, it can be seen that there is a rapid rise in the acoustic emission count over a small increment of strain just prior to failure. It would be difficult, therefore, to predict the beginning of specimen failure although it can be said that catastrophic failure takes

place after a strain of 0.0025 in/in. It appears that severe damage is not present until this value is exceeded. Figure 5 shows the acoustic emission count as a function of composite strain for both specimens (Figures 3a and 4), where the acoustic emission count is plotted on a linear rather than on a logarithmic scale, and illustrates the above condition more clearly. In reviewing photomicrograph and scanning electron microscope pictures for one of these specimens after fracture (associated with Figure 3), other relevant composite fracture characteristics can be seen. Figure 6 shows the fracture line of the composite specimen for most of the specimen width. It can be noticed that there is some fiber uncoated fibers with what appear to be very small droplets of solidified aluminum on them. This appears to indicate that the graphite fiber in this region of the composite were either not completely infiltrated and wetted by the aluminum alloy during fabrication, or that excessive local temperature during hot pressing of the infiltrated tow caused dewetting and debonding. Figure 7 is a scanning electron microscope picture of this specimen at higher magnification; it shows smaller sections of the specimen along the fracture line. Fiber pullout and misaligned fibers are clearly evident, together with some broken off fibers.

The maximum fiber pullout length shown in Figure 7, together with the known fiber strength and diameter, permit the estimation of the aluminum-graphite fiber interfacial shear strength

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_f d}{4\ell}$$

where τ is the interfacial shear strength at the aluminum-graphite fiber interface (psi); σ_f is the fiber tensile strength, 320,000 psi; d is the fiber diameter, 6.6 microns; and ℓ is the maximum fiber pullout length, ≈ 131 microns. Substituting the values of σ_f , d , and ℓ respectively in the above equation, the interfacial shear strength is found to be 4,000 psi.

Figure 8a shows the acoustic emission count and stress as a function of strain for boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 6061 (the specimen cross-sectional area 0.201" x 0.042"; the number of fibers ranges from 154 to 171). Figure 8b shows the acoustic emission rate and stress as a function of strain for the same specimen. It can be noticed that the acoustic emission count (21,400 near fracture) and rate (approaching 400 counts/sec near fracture) are much greater for this specimen than for the graphite fiber reinforced aluminum specimens. It also can be noticed that the variations in the acoustic emission rate is much more pronounced.

Figure 9a again shows the acoustic emission count and stress as a function of strain for boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 6061 (the specimen cross-sectional area is 0.204" x 0.040"; the number of fibers range from 149-166); and Figure 9b shows the

acoustic emission rate and stress as a function of strain for the same specimen. It can be noticed that the acoustic emission count (36,000 near fracture) and rate (approaching 800 counts/sec near fracture) for this specimen are larger than the previous specimen.

Figure 10 shows the acoustic emission count as a function of composite strain for these specimens (Figures 8 and 9) where the acoustic emission count rise is more gradual than those shown in Figure 5, over the entire composite stress region which indicates a more gradual degradation of the specimen. However, catastrophic failure does not occur in a short time or small interval of strain.

In comparing the acoustic emission characteristics of the composites, one should bear in mind that the number of fibers in a boron-aluminum alloy 6061 composite specimen is much smaller than the number of fibers in a graphite-aluminum alloy 7000 specimen, but the boron fiber diameter is much larger than the graphite fiber diameter (on the order of 15.4 to 1). Therefore, the cross-sectional area of the boron fiber is approximately 237 times as large as that of the graphite fiber; and the differences in physical size has to be considered when large differences in acoustic emission data arise.

Of interest here are the pronounced variations of the acoustic emission rate for the boron fiber reinforced specimens. These variations (fluctuations) extending from low to high values, during a particular time or strain interval, are probably due to the movement of the fibers relative to the matrix. As the composite specimen is stressed there are shearing and pulling out effects on the fiber from the matrix resulting in a continuous variation of the acoustic emission. One can speculate that the degree of variation is a function of fiber diameter (surface area) and the frictional and bonding conditions which exist between the fibers and the matrix. Simultaneously with the above events, fiber fracture and fiber pull-out are also increasing, which contribute to these variations, so that the acoustic emission rate continuously rises until specimen fracture stress (strain) is reached.

Figures 11 and 12 are photomicrographs, after fracture, of one boron fiber reinforced aluminum specimen whose acoustic emission characteristics are described in Figure 9. The surface layer of aluminum was dissolved in order to reveal the underlying condition of the fibers. Figure 11 shows the multiple fractures of the fibers and the fracture of the matrix along the fracture line. The multiple fractures indicate that the fiber matrix bond of the broken or discontinuous fibers was so good that they continued to carry some load. These multiple fractures also appear to be an energy absorbing mechanism. Figure 12 shows specific areas of the same specimen and reveal in greater detail the severity of multiple fiber fracture. Most of the multiple fiber fractures occur near the fracture line of the composite; and many of the fractured fiber elements have lengths

which are as small or smaller than the diameter of the fiber. Also, many of these small fiber fractures are probably due to the shock wave generated during failure of the specimen. Figure 13 is a scanning electron microscope picture of this same specimen after fracture, and clearly reveals debonding between the basic laminae which were hot pressed to form the original composite, and also fiber matrix debonding. Although the former effect indicates a flawed composite fabrication technique, both types of debonding are good energy absorbing mechanisms which can delay catastrophic failure. Figure 14 is a photomicrograph of the other specimen, after fracture, whose acoustic emission characteristics are shown in Figure 8. It can be seen that similar results in composite fiber fracture are obtained as before.

Figure 15 is a representative photomicrograph of boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 2024, a different specimen type, taken from a section of the plate material. Although the fibers from this section are fairly well distributed, there is some fiber-fiber contact. The average fiber diameter is now 4.0 mils (instead of 5.6 mils).

Figure 16a shows the acoustic emission count and stress for boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 2024 (the specimen cross-section area is 0.183" x 0.100"; the number of fibers is 584); and Figure 16b shows the acoustic emission rate and stress as a function of strain for the same specimens (1). It can be noted that the acoustic emission count (141,000 near fracture) and rate (3000 counts/sec near fracture) are greater than those of the previous specimens. The boron fiber diameter is still much larger than the graphite fiber diameter (on the order of 21.6 to 1); the cross-sectional area of the boron fiber is approximately 465 times as large as that of the graphite fiber.

In comparing the two boron fiber composite types, the boron fiber reinforced aluminum 2024 specimen has 3.5 times as many fibers approximately as boron fiber reinforced aluminum 6061, but the fiber diameter is smaller (4.0 mils as compared to 5.6 mils). In comparing the acoustic emission data for the two composite types, the acoustic emission rate for boron fiber reinforced aluminum 2024 is much greater than that of boron fiber reinforced aluminum 6061 (on the order of 3000 counts/sec to 800 counts/sec); the number of fibers present is greater also. It would seem that the acoustic rate (for similar composite types) is dependent on the number of fibers present, while sharp variations in acoustic emission rate are highly dependent on fiber diameter (together with the particular frictional and bonding conditions in the composite).

Figure 17a shows the acoustic emission count and stress for another specimen of boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 2024 (the specimen cross-sectional area is 0.192" x 0.100"; the number of

fibers is 613); and Figure 17b shows the acoustic emission rate and stress as a function of strain for the same specimen. It can be noted that the acoustic emission count (138,900 near fracture) and rate 3000 counts/sec near fracture) are near to those values of the previous specimen. The fall off in the acoustic emission rate, near a strain of 0.001 in/in, is attributable to the momentary slippage of the specimen in the grips of the tension test unit.

Figure 18 shows the acoustic emission count and composite strain for the two specimens contained in Figure 16a and Figure 17a, where the acoustic emission count is plotted on a linear rather than on a logarithmic scale. One characteristic which can be readily noticed is that a linear relationship exists for the acoustic emission count versus strain in the region extending from 0.0015 in/in to 0.004 in/in. After a strain of 0.004 in/in is exceeded for both specimens, the acoustic emission count begins to rise very rapidly, now being of the power-law type, which probably indicates that for all practical purposes the specimen is structurally ineffective. It is believed that the acoustic emission, before the composite strain of 0.004 in/in, is primarily due to some fiber fracture and fiber pullout; and after this strain value is exceeded, the acoustic emission is still due to fiber fracture and fiber pull-out which are now exceedingly large in number, but with the added effects of interface failure and severe matrix cracking.

Figure 19 is a photomicrograph of the boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy specimen after fracture whose acoustic emission characteristics are described in Figure 17. Here, some of the aluminum has been dissolved exposing some of the broken fibers. Figure 19 shows specific areas of the specimen and show that multiple fiber fracture occurred again. Although the degree of fiber fracture is great for boron fiber reinforced aluminum 2024, the severity of fiber fracture appears to be greater for boron fiber reinforced aluminum 6061.

In order to establish a general reference so that comparisons in acoustic emission results could be made, the acoustic emission count and stress as a function of strain for aluminum 2024 (the specimen cross-sectional area is 0.200" x 0.081") without fibers, were obtained. In Figure 20a, it can be noted that as stress is applied on the aluminum specimen, the acoustic emission count begins to rise in the elastic region and slows in rising in the plastic region. The total count (events) obtained is small being on the order of 30 counts. Figure 20b also shows the acoustic emission rate and stress as a function of strain for the same specimen. As anticipated, the average acoustic emission rate is also small, below 0.5 counts/sec. One can mention at this time, that this specimen is relatively quiet; and one can only speculate at this time that microcracks and microflaws are probably the primary contributing sources of the acoustic emission.

In summary, the acoustic emission count and rate from graphite and boron fiber reinforced aluminums, because of the energies released during fiber fracture and fiber pullout, show marked differences and are much greater than for the aluminum alone. It can be mentioned that large variations in acoustic emission, as well as in the stress-strain data are possible for many fiber reinforced materials due to deficiencies which may be present but which can be eliminated in future composite development programs. (2) These deficiencies could include variations in density due to uneven fiber distribution, fiber-fiber contact and some areas of poor metal-metal and metal-fiber bond. Insofar as discussing which composite fiber types would be preferable, the preference would be determined as to where the composite material is to be used as a structural element and would also have to be based on the particular properties or characteristics desired. Undoubtedly, many more studies related to acoustic emission, composite stress-strain relationships, composite properties, and composite refinement would be needed. Table I shows the composite characteristics of all the composite material types considered in this study.

Conclusions

Graphite fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 7000 shows a sharp increase in acoustic emission count and rate over a small increment of strain just prior to failure. Therefore, it would be difficult to predict the beginning of specimen failure except that catastrophic failure takes place after a specific value of strain is reached. It also appears that severe specimen damage is not present until this value is exceeded.

Boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 6061, shows a more gradual rise in acoustic emission count and rate over the entire composite strain region but also indicates a gradual degradation of the specimen. However, catastrophic failure does not occur in a small time or strain interval.

Boron fiber reinforced aluminum alloy 2024 shows characteristics in acoustic emission data similar to those of boron fiber reinforced aluminum 6061. The acoustic emission count obtained from the former show a distinct linear portion and a power-law portion over the entire strain region.

All of the above results are based on a limited number of specimens. It is realized that much more experimental data would be desirable. However, preliminary data obtained here show that large variations in acoustic emission as well as in the stress-strain data are possible for similar composite-types. These variations could be due to deficiencies which may be present but which could be eliminated in future fiber composite development programs. Some of these deficiencies, which need to be considered include uneven fiber distribution, fiber-fiber contact, and some areas of poor metal-metal and metal-fiber bond.

References

1. Grenis, A. F. and Rudy, F. J., "Fracture Characteristics of Boron Fiber Reinforced Aluminum 2024 as Detected by Acoustic Emission," Army Materials and Mechanics Research Center, Watertown, MA, AMMRC TR 73-57, December 1973.
2. DiCesare, "Characterization of 2024 Aluminum-Boron Fiber Composites," Army Materials and Mechanics Research Center, Watertown, MA, AMMRC TN 73-10, June 1973.
3. Liptai, R. G., (General Chairman), "Acoustic Emission", ASTM Special Publication 505, (Acoustic Emission Working Group Subcommittee Report: Recommended Acoustic Terminology), American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, PA, pp. 335-337.

Table 1. COMPOSITE CHARACTERISTICS

Composite type	Area cross-section (in x in)	Volume fraction %	Fiber diameter	Number of fibers	AE Count (total)	Fracture stress (ksi)	Fracture strain (in/in)	Modulus 10 ⁶ psi
Al 7000 & C fibers	0.249 x 0.041	31 - 36	6.6 microns	59,700 - 69,300	14,896	48.6	0.00282	19.3
Al 7000 & C fibers	0.252 x 0.039	31 - 36	6.6 microns	57,500 - 66,700	9,648	58.8	0.00315	20.0
Al 6061 & B fibers	0.201 x 0.042	45 - 50	5.6 mils	154 - 171	21,400	157.1	0.0065	25.7
Al 6061 & B fibers	0.204 x 0.040	45 - 50	5.6 mils	149 - 166	36,000	133.6	0.0047	28.4
Al 2024 & B fibers	0.183 x 0.100	40.1	4.0 mils	584	141,400	114.8	0.00538	22.5
Al 2024 & B fibers	0.192 x 0.100	40.1	4.0 mils	613	138,900	97.4	0.00435	26.7
Al 2024 (alone)	0.200 x 0.081	---	---	---	28.5	---	---	20.6 9.22

1. Acoustic emission equipment.

2. Graphite fiber reinforced aluminum 7000, X1000.

3. Acoustic emission and composite stress as a function of composite strain for graphite fiber reinforced aluminum 7000.

4. Acoustic emission count and composite stress as a function of composite strain for graphite fiber reinforced aluminum 7000.
5. Acoustic emission count as a function of composite strain for graphite fiber reinforced aluminum 7000.

6. Graphite fiber reinforced aluminum 7000, X48.

7. Graphite fiber reinforced aluminum 7000, Mag. 325X.

8. Acoustic emission and composite stress as a function of composite strain for boron fiber reinforced aluminum 6061.

9. Acoustic emission and composite stress as a function of composite strain for boron fiber reinforced aluminum 6061.

10. Acoustic emission count as a function of composite strain for boron fiber reinforced aluminum 6061.

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11. Boron fiber reinforced aluminum 6061, Mag. 50X.

12. Boron fiber reinforced aluminum 6061, Mag. 200X.

13. Boron fiber reinforced aluminum 6061, Mag. 80X.

14. Boron fiber reinforced aluminum 6061, Mag. 200X.

15. Boron fiber reinforced aluminum 2024, Mag. 100X.

16. Acoustic emission and composite stress as a function of composite strain for boron fiber reinforced aluminum 2024.

17. Acoustic emission and composite stress as a function of composite strain for boron fiber-reinforced aluminum 2024.

18. Acoustic emission count as a function of composite strain for boron fiber-reinforced aluminum 2024.

19. Boron fiber reinforced aluminum 2024, X200.

20. Acoustic emission and stress as a function of strain for aluminum 2024.